

Desert Culture///

The cluster examines the domestic and community-focused built environment of the Arabian Peninsula, exploring its various typologies, responses to climate and culture, the creators of these structures, and their users. It also investigates how educational and international networks shaped and influenced these developments while being inspired by them.

By analysing spaces through architectural, anthropological, environmental, and socio-cultural lenses, the research aims to develop a digital archive—a “repository”—that consolidates previously undocumented material and captures the stories and lived memories of a rich and vibrant ‘desert culture’.

Award Letter 2022- *Grant Activity Code: R21105*

Cluster Research: **“Desert Culture”**

Zayed University, UAE

DESERT CULTURE CLUSTER 2022-24

Cooler Desert Cities $\approx \Delta^\circ$

(P3) Research Project: “Cooler Desert Cities” initiative or how desert cultures have translated the local climate and existing material context into climate responsive and culturally sensitive architecture and urban design.

By examining traditional knowledge inherent in traditional desert buildings/neighborhoods/cities, this project seeks to uncover design drivers for low-emission, low energy desert comfort for net-zero desert architecture and communities. The research examines case studies on the Arabian peninsula, investigating how architectural and urban design solutions have been tailored to mitigate the impact of harsh climatic conditions. We employ Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) modelling to glean insights from traditional urbanisation practices. The objective is to extract knowledge embedded in carefully selected traditional case studies and apply it to inform contemporary architecture. The focus centers on analysing the impacts of design measures on the local environment, particularly in mitigating factors like urban heat stress. The synthesis of climate-responsive strategies with cultural nuances offers a framework for creating sustainable and culturally attuned urban environments in today's desert cities. The study contributes to the discourse on merging tradition with innovation in architectural and urban design, particularly in regions where climatic challenges shape the built environment.

DESERT CULTURE CLUSTER 2022-25

